

Obedience And Quality Of Public Servicesin The County :

A Case Study In Kediri Regency

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Abstract: In Kediri Regency, standard obedience in public services is a necessity in the implementation of public services. During 2015 until 2018, the level of obedience of the government in Kediri Regency in the standard of public services fluctuated. The index of public services of the government in Kediri Regency was included in quadrant three so that it is a necessity to have extra improvements. This study aimed to analyze the level of obedience in the standard of public services in improving the quality of public services. The research methods used in this study were literature study and secondary data analysis. The main result and conclusion of this study showed that the obedience in the standard of public services in Kediri Regency was in a high level, but the quality of public services was not in a good condition.

Keywords : Obedience, Public Services, Quality

I. INTRODUCTION

Qualified public service or known as excellent service is the best service that fulfills the standard of service quality. Based on the Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning public services, the standard of service is an indicator that is used as a guidance of the service implementation and a reference of the assessment of service quality as obligation and promise of the service implementation to the society due to the qualified, fast, easy, affordable, and measurable service. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 15 of 2014 concerning Guidelines for Service Standards, service standard components related to the service delivery process include requirements, procedures, service period, costs/tariffs, service products, and complaint handling.

In the public sector, service is said to be excellent if 1) the best service derives from the government to the customer/service user, 2) there are standards of service, 3) it exceeds the standard or equals to the standard, if there is no standard, the best service can be provided, services that are close to what is considered standard services and performed optimally (Sedarmayanti, 2009). Meanwhile, (Islamy, M Irfan, 2002) mentioned that there are some principles of the excellent service to realize the vision of good governance: 1) Appropriateness, 2) Accessibility, 3) Continuity, 4) Technicality, 5) Profitability, 6) Equitability, 7) Transparency, 8) Accountability, 9) Effectiveness and Efficiency. If a government agency and other institutions are able to implement the standard and be innovative in providing the service, that can be said that the government agency and institutions have provided the best service quality.

Moreover, there were researches related to public service. Those researches can be divided into 2 (two) main tendencies. First, studies analyzing Public Service Motivation (PSM) that generally discussed an employee having motivation in providing public services (Wright et al., 2017), (Liu et al., 2018), (Kim, 2018), (Ward, 2019), (Budiyanti et al., 2019), (Pratama & Nurhidayah, 2019). Second, studies that looked at public service delivery organizations in providing public services (Tuurnas, 2015), (Klierova & Kutik, 2017), (Negoita,

2018),(Pesti & Randma-Liiv, 2018),(Shobaruddin, 2019). At the point, there were various approaches that had been applied to research public services. The results of those studies were generally not much different, that the motivation of employees in providing public services was still lacking. The organization also had difficulties in controlling opportunistic behavior of employees in providing public services.

Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services is the commitment of the Government of Indonesia in improving the quality of public services. In addition, Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government is directed to accelerate the realization of welfare of the people through improving services, empowerment, and community participation, as well as enhancing regional competitiveness by taking into account the principles of democracy, equity, justice, and the uniqueness of a region.

The Ombudsman as a state institution has the authority to oversee the administration of public services both administered by state and government administrators including those held by State-Owned Enterprises, Regional-Owned Enterprises, and State-Owned Legal Entities as well as private entities or individuals who are tasked with carrying out certain public services that some or all of the funds come from the state budget and/or regional budget. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 37 Year 2008 concerning the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia, the Ombudsman also has the task of a) receiving reports on the alleged maladministration in the administration of public services; b) examining the substance of the Report; c) following up on Reports covered by the Ombudsman's scope of authority; d) carrying out an investigation on its own initiative of the alleged Administration in the administration of public services; e) coordinating and cooperating with state institutions or other government institutions as well as community and private institutions; f) building networks; g) making efforts to prevent maladministration in the administration of public services; and h) performing other tasks given by the law. Thus, the Ombudsman has the responsibility of maintaining the implementation of the quality of public services in accordance with the standards set by the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform organized by the state and government administrators.

Based on the Ombudsman's report on obedience assessment in 2018 conducted at 9 Ministries, 4 Institutions, 16 Provinces, 49 City Governments, and 199 Regency Governments carried out by the Central Team and the Indonesian Ombudsman Representative Team in 34 Representative Offices of the Indonesian Ombudsman, the Central Team assessed a number of Ministries and Institutions, while the Representative Team assessed the Provincial Government, Regency Government, City Government and a number of Vertical Agencies.

The assessment of the fulfillment of service standard components in 199 Regency Governments in Indonesia showed that as much as 24.12% or 48 regency governments belonged into the red zone with the predicate of low obedience, 44.22% or 88 regency governments belonged into the yellow zone with the predicate of moderate obedience, and 31.66% or 63 regency governments were included in the green zone with the predicate of high obedience.

II. METHODS

This study used a qualitative approach, which is ontologically characterized by the fact that the researchers constructed the reality that is seen epistemologically based on the value and judgment of the value of the researchers who guide and shape research conclusions based on reality - sensitivity - consequences of changes and differences in values, which are socially negotiated and correctly recognized, and qualitative research is empirical and scientific. The qualitative approach strategy is used to answer the phenomenon (Creswell, 2010)

The sources of this study were secondary data obtained from the ombudsman report for 4 (four) years. The researchers managed the secondary data by comparing data annually. The secondary data were also obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (*BPS*) on the Public Service Index (*IPP*). As the data validity, the researchers conducted triangulation, which is a data collection technique that combines data from various existing data sources and different time intervals. The analysis of the data in this study was the qualitative data analysis of the Spradley model as the steps described in the following: domain analysis, taxonomic analysis, componential analysis and discovering cultural theme.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Obedience and Quality of Public Services at the Government of Kediri Regency

The Government of Kediri Regency is a regency area in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. In the development of the Indonesian Government Effectiveness Index (GEI) for the last 3 (three) years from 2015 to 2017, it was awarded a GEI value of 45.67 in 2015; it received a GEI score of 52.88 in 2016; and it got a GEI value of 54.81 in 2017. Based on those data, the value of GEI increased by 7.21 in 2015 to 2016, while the value of GEI increased by 1.93 in 2016 to 2017, as shown below:

Fig. 1. Government Effectiveness Index of the Indonesian Government 2015 – 2017.

Source: Data processed from Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) 2015-2017

The Indonesian Government improves the quality of governance through the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform, the State Civil Apparatus Commission (*KASN*) and the Ombudsman. *KASN* was formed based on Law Number 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus (*ASN*), as stated in article 28 of the *ASN* Law, *KASN* has the purpose of a) ensuring the realization of a Merit System in *ASN* policy and Management, b) realizing a professional, high-performance, prosperous *ASN*, and serves as the glue of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, c) supporting the implementation of effective, efficient and open state government, and being free from practices of Corruption, Collusion, Nepotism, d) realizing neutral *ASN* employees and not distinguishing the people served by ethnicity, religion, race and class, e) ensuring the formation of the *ASN* profession that is respected by its employees and the society, and f) realizing a dynamic and cultured performance achievement of *ASN*.

The Ombudsman as a state institution has the authority to oversee the implementation of public services both organized by state and government administrators including those held by State-Owned Enterprises, Regional-Owned Enterprises, and State-Owned Legal Entities as well as private entities or individuals who are tasked with carrying out certain public services in which some or all of the funds sourced from the state revenue and expenditure budget and/or regional revenue and expenditure budget. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 37 Year 2008 Concerning the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia, the Ombudsman also has the task of a) receiving reports on the alleged Maladministration in the administration of public services; b) examining the substance of the Report; c) following up on Reports covered by the Ombudsman's scope of authority; d) carrying out an investigation on its own initiative of the alleged Maladministration in the administration of public services; e) coordinating and cooperating with state institutions or other government institutions as well as community and private institutions; f) building networks; g) making efforts to prevent Maladministration in the administration of public services; and h) performing other tasks given by the law. Thus, the Ombudsman has the responsibility of maintaining the implementation of the

quality of public services in accordance with the standards set by the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform organized by the state and government administrators.

Regulation of the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia Number 22 of 2016, on changes of Regulation of the Ombudsman of the Republic of Indonesia Number 17 of 2015 Concerning Obedience Assessment towards Public Service Standards is a regulation aimed at accelerating the improvement of the quality of public services in Indonesia.

Based on the report of the Ombudsman on obedience assessment in 2018 conducted at 9 Ministries, 4 Institutions, 16 Provinces, 49 City Governments, and 199 Regency Governments carried out by the Central Team and the Indonesian Ombudsman Representative Team in 34 Representative Offices of the Indonesian Ombudsman, the Central Team assessed a number of Ministries and Institutions, while the Representative Team assessed the Provincial Government, Regency Government, City Government and a number of Vertical Agencies.

The assessment of the fulfillment of service standard components in 199 Regency Governments in Indonesia showed that 24.12% or 48 regency governments belonged into the red zone with the predicate of low obedience, 44.22% or 88 regency governments belonged into the yellow zone with the predicate of moderate obedience, and 31.66% or 63 regency governments were included in the green zone with the predicate of high obedience.

At the level of Regency Government, the obedience zoning movement has relatively improved. In 2017, the number of Regency Governments including in the green zone totaled 13 or 12.15% of the total of 107 Regency Governments that were objects in 2017. In 2018, there were 63 Regency Governments including in the green zone or 31.66% of the total of 199 Regencies that were objects in 2017.

The Government of Kediri Regency is a regency that has experienced a significant increase in obedience zoning. It received a red zone in 2017, but it occupied the third green zone with a value of 99.49 in 2018. In addition, Pasaman Barat Regency, Batang Regency, and Sambas Regency were some of the regencies that had succeeded in increasing zoning in 2018, which was to become a green zone which previously acquired a yellow zone in 2017. The Ciamis Regency with a value of 99.96 and Pematang Regency with a value of 99.70 were the 2 (two) top green zone regencies which were used as objects of the assessment in 2018, but they were included in the green zone. Meanwhile, the Government of the Yapen Islands Regency and Keerom Regency were still stagnant in the red zone, even for Konawe Selatan Regency, the zonation decreased from the yellow zone in 2017 to the red zone in 2018, as shown in the following table:

Table 1. Comparison of Zoning of Regency Government 2017-2018.

Regency	Zoning of Obedience Assessment	
	2017	2018
Kediri	Red Zone	Green Zone
Pasaman Barat	Yellow Zone	Green Zone
Batang	Yellow Zone	Green Zone
Sambas	Yellow Zone	Green Zone
Ciamis		Green Zone
Pematang		Green Zone
Kepulauan Yapen	Red Zone	Red Zone
Keerom	Red Zone	Red Zone
Konawe Selatan	Yellow Zone	Red Zone

Source: Ombudsman Report 2018

Based on the data of Ombudsman report 2018, the government of Kediri Regency was a regency that had experienced a significant increase in obedience zoning, in the green zone from the red zone in 2017. However, from 2015 to 2018, Kediri Regency was included as an obedience assessment regency by the Ombudsman. The

results of the obedience assessment of Kediri Regency from 2015 to 2018 showed a fluctuating trend. The comparison of zoning of Kediri Regency in 2015-2018 was shown below:

Fig. 2. Comparison of Zoning of Kediri Regency 2015-2018.

Source: Data processed from Ombudsman Report 2015-2018

Based on those data, it can be explained that the Government of Kediri Regency for the level of obedience of public service standards had fluctuating values and zoning in 2015-2018. In 2015, the obedience value of Kediri Regency was 54.12 (the yellow zone). In 2016, the obedience value of Kediri Regency was 79.73 (the yellow zone). In 2017, the obedience value of Kediri Regency was 50.88 (the red zone). In 2018, the obedience value of Kediri Regency was 99.49 (the green zone).

For two years, Kediri Regency was included in the yellow zone category, namely in 2015 and 2016. Besides, during those two years, there was an increase in the obedience value by 25.61 in Kediri Regency. In 2017, the obedience value of Kediri Regency was expected to increase, but that was not as expected because the obedience value of Kediri Regency had decreased by 28.85 so that Kediri Regency was included in the red zone with a value of 50.88.

In 2018, Kediri Regency had a significant change with a obedience value of 99.49 (the green zone) from a value of 50.88 (the red zone) in 2017. However, it did not mean that behind the award it received, the issue of public services no longer existed.

The fact showed a contradiction. Based on the Survey of the Results of the Implementation of Bureaucracy Reform (*SHPRB*) of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucracy Reform collaborated with the Central Statistics Agency (*BPS*) in 2018, in which the results of the survey were in the form of Public Service Index (*IPP*) and Anti-Corruption Perception Index (*IPAK*), Kediri Regency obtained an *IPP* value of 3.01 and an *IPAK* value of 3.32. Thus, Kediri Regency was included in the category of quadrant 3 (three) which showed the condition in which the *IPP* and *IPAK* values were lower than the specified passing grade value. The value of each element of the Public Service Index (*IPP*) is shown below:

Table 2. Value of Public Service Index (IPP)

Element of Assessment of IPP	Procedure	Requirements	Cost	Time	Resolution	Response	Performance	Facilities	Complaints	IPP
Kediri Regency	3.19	3.17	3.02	3.06	2.94	2.99	3.11	3.07	2.50	3.01

Source: Report of SHPRB BPS 2018

Based on those data, the government of Kediri Regency was included in quadrant 3 (three) so that more intense coaching is necessary because it requires extra improvements, both in the physical aspect (service).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The level of obedience at public service standards in Kediri Regency had fluctuating values in 2015 - 2018 with a value of 54.12 (the yellow zone) in 2015, a value of 79.73 (the yellow zone) in 2016, a value of 50.88 (the red zone) in 2017, and a value of 99.49 (the green zone) in 2018. The Public Service Index (IPP) of the Government of Kediri Regency obtained a value of 3.01, showing that the quality of public services at the Government of Kediri Regency still needs to be improved, especially in the elements of resolution, response and complaints.

Based on the findings from the comparative data, it showed that the high level of obedience at public service standards was not necessarily followed by good quality public services. Further research can analyze the facts in the field through primary data that is taken more in depth by researchers to find the root of the problem of the quality of public services at the Government of Kediri Regency.

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